

**THE CLASSIFICATION OF BORROWED WORDS IN ENGLISH
LANGUAGE**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7539610>

Annotation: In this article, words from the English language, words from the past, different effects on the enrichment of debts in languages, also apply to phonetic design, stress and spelling, words from the Russian language, derivative morphemes also o. Information was obtained on the assimilation of debt data.

Keywords: Debt, assimilation, appearance, phonetic design, stress, spelling, dictionary, rhymes, prepositions, hybrid.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilidagi so'zlar, o'tmishdagi so'zlar, tillardagi qarzlarni boyitishda turli xil ta'sirlar, shuningdek, fonetik dizayn, urg'u va imlo, rus tilidagi so'zlarga, hosila morfemalarga ham tegishli. Qarz ma'lumotlarini o'zlashtirish bo'yicha ma'lumot olindi.

Kalit so'zlar: Qarz, assimilyatsiya, ko'rinish, fonetik dizayn, urg'u, imlo, lug'at, olmoshlar, yuklamalar, duragay.

Аннотация: В этой статье слова из английского языка, слова из прошлого, различные воздействия на обогащение долгов в языках, также относятся к фонетическому оформлению, ударению и орфографии, слова из русского языка, производные морфемы также о. Была получена информация об усвоении данных о долге.

Ключевые слова: долг, ассимиляция, внешний вид, фонетическое оформление, ударение, орфография, словарь, рифмы, предлоги, гибрид.

It is impossible to imagine a language that does not borrow from a foreign language. Thus, English has many words from Ancient Rome, Greece, Italy, Spain, Germany, and Russia. Most of them were assimilated and had a completely English appearance. Others, depending on the similarity of the organization, make an existing sound to the English pronunciation norms, for example, German kindergarten, shnapps, zeppelin or Russian tundra, steppe words. The composition of these debts was assimilated, lost its "national" image, and was adopted by the British as their homeland. This also applies to phonetic design, stress, and spelling.

A dictionary that has different effects on the enrichment of debts in different languages ... In some languages it has no effect on the vocabulary of the

language. In other languages, borrowing in different historical periods has such a great impact on the vocabulary of the language that even service words such as rhymes, prepositions from other languages replace their original services.

To prove that this language has not lost its originality, despite the fact that many words in English are words derived from other languages.

In language history, borrowings from other languages are usually considered depending on the period in which the language existed. In other words, all debts are considered at the same time in a given period.

1. Borrowing from the Russian language is considered by studying the state of the English dictionary.
2. Learn how to get a loan into English.
3. The role of debt words is considered.
4. The level of assimilation of borrowed words is checked.

During its long history of development, English has adopted a large number of foreign words that have entered the dictionary in one way or another. These words include both service words and derivative morphemes. Nevertheless, the English language has not lost its originality. It has retained its originality and distinction from other languages.

The modern dictionary of the English language has changed and supplemented over the centuries and now has a large number of words, which has had an indefinite effect on the formation of its vocabulary. However, despite this, English did not become a unique “hybrid” and never lost its originality.

Thus, in the process of work, foreign languages had a greater impact on the development of English than the development of many other European languages.

English, without being confined to any frame, has not lost its ‘face’; it remained the language of a German group with all the peculiarities of the whole period of development, and changes in borrowing only enriched its vocabulary.

In contrast, modern French can be called the state language of France, whose speakers are deeply concerned about the purity of the language, trying to distinguish it from foreign language news.

Lexical units from about 50 languages of the world make up about 70% of the English dictionary, and they include layers of vocabulary derived from different historical periods and different - historical, geographical, social, economic influences. cultural and others. - Conditions for the development and existence of the English language. As a result of the long historical interaction of languages, borrowing as a process and borrowing as a result of this process is of

great interest for language history, in which they learn in detail about the reasons for borrowing and source languages. methods, forms and types of borrowing, as well as changes in the language in which the borrowed word received it. Debts are primarily concerned with the influence of a particular language on the structural structure of word combinations, as well as their specificity, if a number of genetic features are preserved, the status of the language in which they are obtained.

Conclusion.

Thus, by studying the history of the English language, I can draw clear conclusions by analyzing the etymology of the words derived from the English language.

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